

(figure, e). The receptive female remained quiescent, lifted her wings, and further curved her abdomen (copulatory acceptance posture) (figure, d). After the female accepted the male, the pair immediately turned 180° (figure, f), hung upside down for a second (figure, g), and landed on a substrate, assuming a posterior-to-posterior copulation orientation. Unless the pair was disturbed,

mating was quiescent; wing movement and antenna vibration ceased (figure, h).

Aside from the sex pheromones females released during calling, both sexes most likely release other olfactory and tactile stimuli for copulation to occur. Further investigations are necessary to verify these stimuli and identify their specific functions. □

Diagrammatic representation of *M. panalis* mating sequence.

Population fluctuation of leaffolder (LF) at different planting times in some rice varieties

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Rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* is a serious pest in Andhra Pradesh when planting extends from Jul to mid-Sep because of varied rainfall.

We studied the effect of four planting times on LF incidence in BPT2740, BPT11978, MTU6861, MTU2400, and MTU7029.

Varieties were planted in a split-plot design with three replications. No insecticide was used. Total leaves and damaged leaves were counted on 20 randomly selected hills/plot, 60 d after transplanting.

LF damage increased significantly with delayed planting date. There was no difference in damage among the varieties (see table). □

Effect of planting time on LF incidence. RRU, Bapatla, AP, India, 1986-87 kharif.

Planting time	Damaged leaves ^a (%)
15 Aug 1986	37.7
30 Aug 1986	47.8
15 Sep 1986	57.3
30 Sep 1986	64.8
Mean	
LSD	1.9

^a Values are angular transformations.

Survey of ricefield insects in Mbo and Ndog Plains of Cameroon

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Rice is mainly produced in the northern Sahelian Region of Cameroon. The rest is cultivated in the Western Highland Savanna, mainly in the Mbo and Ndog Plains, with an estimated 210 ha and 3,000 ha of irrigated rice, respectively.

During the 1987-89 survey, we collected and documented insect species

present, identified insect damage, and documented beneficial insects.

Insects were collected from an advanced yield trial plot (1,080 m²) surrounded by other irrigated ricefields.

We collected 24 times (12 night and 12 day) from transplanting to crop maturity. Collections were from late Jul to early Nov in Ndop and late Sep to mid-

Dec in Mbo. A hurricane light trap centrally installed collected noctuids from nightfall to dawn (11h). Day collections were made at 11:00 a.m. with sweep net.

We collected over 40 insect species during the 2-yr survey. The table lists the 20 most prevalent species. □

Using chlorpyrifos to control gall midge (GM)

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Efficacy of foliar spraying and seed soaking with 0.05% and 0.1% chlorpyrifos to control GM *Orseolia oryzae* in rice nurseries was evaluated during the 1988 wet season.

Seven treatments (see table) replicated four times were arranged in randomized complete block design. We sowed on 28 Aug in 1-× 1-m plots.

Tikkana (NLR27999) seed was soaked in chlorpyrifos solution for 12 h, then incubated for 36 h; sprouted seed was soaked for 3 h. Seed for the foliar spray treatment and control was soaked in water and incubated. Chlorpyrifos was sprayed 10 d after sowing (DAS).

We assessed percent GM incidence (exposed silver shoots and suppressed galls) by randomly pulling 200 seedlings per treatment at 10-d intervals from 25 DAS onwards.

Treatments showed significant differences at 25 and 35 DAS. Insecticidal efficacy was not significant at 45 DAS (see table). Chlorpyrifos treatments

GM incidence in the nursery with chlorpyrifos treatments.

Treatment	GM incidence ^a (%)		
	25 DAS	35 DAS	45 DAS
T1 Foliar spray of chlorpyrifos 0.05% at 10 DAS	10.5 (18.8)	17.7 (24.7)	37.8 (37.8)
T2 Foliar spray of chlorpyrifos 0.1% at 10 DAS	6.0 (14.1)	21.8 (27.2)	24.7 (29.6)
T3 Soaking of seeds in chlorpyrifos 0.05%	10.6 (18.9)	28.8 (32.4)	38.0 (37.9)
T4 Soaking of sprouted seeds in chlorpyrifos 0.05%	17.2 (24.3)	40.7 (39.4)	23.2 (28.7)
T5 Soaking of seeds in chlorpyrifos 0.1%	7.1 (15.4)	23.3 (28.2)	37.5 (37.6)
T6 Soaking of sprouted seeds in chlorpyrifos 0.1%	17.7 (24.7)	36.9 (37.4)	36.3 (36.5)
T7 Untreated check	24.2 (29.4)	41.6 (40.1)	33.5 (33.3)
LSD (P=0.05)	4.27	8.06	ns ^b
CV (%)	13.77	16.49	13.34

^aFigures in parentheses are angular transformed values.
^bNonsignificant by *F* test.

Relative prevalence of 20 insect species collected from irrigated plots in 2 rice-growing areas in Cameroon.

Common and scientific name	Relative prevalence ^a (%)		Remarks
	MBo	Ndop	
Stalk-eyed borer - Diopsidae: <i>Diopsis macrophthalma</i> (Dalman)	18.3	33.4	A major rice stem borer
Rice bug - Alydidae: <i>Leptocoris oratorius</i> (Fabricius)	10.1	1.8	Feed on ripening rice grain
Brown stink bug - Pentatomidae: <i>Euschistus servus</i> (Say)	8.9	1.3	Predaceous on several insects and also plant feeders
Cixiid planthoppers - Cixiidae: <i>Oecleus</i> sp.	8.7	39.2	Can spread virus
Long-horned grasshoppers - Tettigoniidae: <i>Conocephalus</i> sp.	8.2	5.4	Predators of rice bugs and stem borer eggs; also leaf feeders
Black lady beetles - Coccinellidae: <i>Hippodamia</i> sp.	6.6	0.1	Predators of many insects, esp. soft-bodied ones
Short-horned grasshoppers - Acrididae: <i>Atractomorpha</i> sp.	6.0	0.2	Plant feeders
Spine-tailed earwigs - Forficulidae: <i>Doru</i> sp.	4.0	0.2	Nocturnal plant feeders
Green stink bugs - Pentatomidae: <i>Nezara viridula</i> (Linn.)	3.5	-	Feed on rice grain during milky, soft dough, and hard dough stages
Cereal leaf beetle-Chrysomelidae: <i>Oulema</i> sp.	3.4	0.3	Foliage feeders
Shield-backed bugs - Scutelleridae: <i>Pharocosis annulus</i>	3.4	0.3	Known to be plant feeders, but feeding activities on the rice plants was not described.
Differential grasshoppers - Acrididae: <i>Melanoplus differentialis</i> (Thomas)	3.0	0.2	Very destructive foliage feeders
Seed bugs - Lygaeidae: <i>Eromocoris ferus</i> (Say)	2.7	1.4	Feed on seeds
Sugarcane borer - Pyralidae: <i>Diatraea saccharidis</i> (Fabricius)	0.2	-	Minor stem borer of rice in the area
Rove beetles - Staphylinidae: <i>Paederus grandis</i> (Aust.)	1.9	-	Known to be predaceous
Harlequin bugs - Pentatomidae: <i>Murgantia histrionica</i> (Hahn)	1.9	-	Found in ricefields, but feeding habit was not described.
African mole crickets - Gryllotalpidae: <i>Gryllotalpa africana</i> Palisot de Beauvois	1.4	-	Cut plants at base and feed on young roots, problem in unflooded fields
Red shouldered stink bugs - Pentatomidae: <i>Thyanta</i> sp.	1.1	0.4	Feed on plant, but not economically important
Ground beetles - Carabidae: <i>Colosoma scrutator</i> (Fabricius)	1.1	0.2	Known to be omnivorous, but activities in the ricefields were not observed.
Damsel bugs - Nabidae: <i>Nabis</i> sp.	0.0	0.1	Predaceous on several insect species

$$^a\text{Relative prevalence \%} = \frac{\text{Total no. of each species}}{\text{Total no. of all species}} \times 100$$

Total no. = Total count for the 12 day sweeps plus the 12 light trap collections per year.

Intensities reported are 1988 and 1989 averages.